

Influence of Resource needs assessment on academic performance of students with disabilities in integrated basic education schools in Nyarugenge district, Rwanda

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21100369>

Published Date: 30-June-2026

Abstract: This study assessed the influence of resource needs assessment on the academic performance of students with disabilities in integrated basic education schools in Nyarugenge District. The study was guided by the objective of examining how resource needs assessment contributes to improving the academic performance of learners with disabilities in inclusive education settings. The study was anchored on the Resource-Based View Theory and Constructivist Learning Theory, which emphasize the importance of adequate educational resources and supportive learning environments in enhancing learners' outcomes. A descriptive survey design using mixed methods was adopted. The target population comprised 885 participants, including headteachers, deputy headteachers, teachers, and students with disabilities from integrated basic education schools in the district. A sample size of 275 respondents was selected using stratified random sampling and purposive sampling techniques. Quantitative data were collected using structured questionnaires, while qualitative data were gathered through interview guides and focus group discussions. The reliability and validity of the research instruments were tested prior to data collection. Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics with the help of SPSS, whereas qualitative data were analyzed through thematic analysis. The findings revealed that resource needs assessment had a significant positive influence on the academic performance of students with disabilities. The overall mean score of 3.987 indicated that respondents strongly agreed that proper assessment of learners' educational resource needs improves academic achievement, participation, and inclusion in classroom activities. Regression analysis further showed that resource needs assessment explained 80.4% ($R^2 = 0.804$) of the variation in academic performance among students with disabilities, demonstrating a strong relationship between the variables. The study concluded that effective resource needs assessment significantly enhances the academic performance of students with disabilities in integrated basic education schools. The study recommended that school administrators, teachers, and education stakeholders should strengthen mechanisms for identifying and addressing the educational resource needs of learners with disabilities to promote inclusive and equitable quality education in Rwanda.

Keywords: Resources Management, Academic Performance, Students, Disabilities, Basic Education Schools, Nyarugenge District.

1. INTRODUCTION

Inclusive education has become a global priority aimed at ensuring equitable access to quality education for learners with disabilities. A key determinant of success in inclusive education is resource needs assessment, which involves identifying the specific learning, assistive, and environmental needs of students with disabilities before providing appropriate support. In countries such as the United States, inclusive education is strongly supported by legislation, particularly the Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA), which requires schools to systematically assess learner needs and provide individualized support through individualized education programs (IEPs), assistive technologies, and specialized

instructional services. These structured needs assessments have been instrumental in improving academic outcomes for students with disabilities by ensuring that interventions are tailored to individual requirements (Smith et al., 2020).

Empirical evidence from developed education systems shows that when resource needs are accurately assessed and addressed, students with disabilities achieve better academic outcomes. Bouck and Cosby (2019) found that learners in inclusive settings performed better in reading and mathematics when their educational needs were properly identified and matched with appropriate instructional support. This highlights that resource needs assessment is not only an administrative process but a critical academic intervention that directly influences learner achievement.

In Europe, inclusive education systems also emphasize structured assessment of learner needs as a foundation for effective support provision. Countries such as Finland, Sweden, and the United Kingdom prioritize identifying learners' specific requirements to guide differentiated instruction, resource allocation, and classroom adaptation strategies (European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education, EASNIE, 2021). Florian and Black-Hawkins (2021) further observed that when teachers effectively assess and respond to diverse learner needs, students with disabilities experience improved cognitive, academic, and social outcomes, demonstrating the central role of needs assessment in inclusive education success.

In Rwanda, inclusive education is guided by national frameworks such as the Special Needs and Inclusive Education Policy (2018) and Vision 2050, which emphasize equitable access to quality education for all learners. The Rwanda Basic Education Board (REB) supports schools in conducting resource needs assessments to identify appropriate learning materials, assistive devices, and instructional support for learners with disabilities (MINEDUC, 2018). Uwimbabazi and Ndayambaje (2021) found that when learner needs are properly assessed and addressed, students with disabilities demonstrate improved academic performance and increased participation in learning activities. However, challenges such as limited funding, shortage of specialized personnel, and weak implementation mechanisms continue to affect the effectiveness of needs assessment practices in integrated basic education schools (Twahirwa, 2020).

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research Design

This study adopted a descriptive survey design.

2.2 Target Population

Slovin's formula was used to determine the appropriate sample size for the study in order to ensure representativeness of the target population while maintaining an acceptable margin of error. The formula is given as:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

n = required sample size

N = total population size

e = margin of error (set at 0.05 for a 95% confidence level)

The study targeted a total population of 885 individuals drawn from headteachers, deputy headteachers, teachers, and students with disabilities in integrated basic education schools in Nyarugenge District. Substituting the values into the formula:

$$\begin{aligned} n &= \frac{885}{1 + 885(0.05)^2} \\ n &= \frac{885}{1 + 885(0.0025)} \\ n &= \frac{885}{1 + 2.2125} \\ n &= \frac{885}{3.2125} \\ n &\approx \mathbf{275} \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the required sample size for the study was 275 respondents.

2.3 Data Collection Procedures

Data for this study were collected using questionnaires, interview guides, and focus group discussions (FGDs). Each tool was designed according to the characteristics of the different categories of respondents to ensure relevant and reliable information. The data collection focused on resource needs assessment and its influence on the academic performance of students with disabilities in integrated basic education schools in Nyarugenge District.

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Demographic characteristics of Respondents

This study analyzed the important information characterizing the respondents. The age group and gender of respondents were among the general information. The results are presented in table and figure as follows:

Table 1: Age group of Respondents

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	21-30	79	29.5
	31-40	120	44.8
	41-50	57	21.3
	Over 50	12	4.5
	Total	268	100.0

Source: Primary data, (2026)

The age group distribution of the respondents is shown in Table 1. The researcher was intrigued by the respondents' age distribution. Of the 268 respondents, 29.5% were between the ages of 21 and 30. Of the respondents, 21.3% were between the ages of 41 and 50, and 44.8% were between the ages of 31 and 40. In contrast, 4.5% of survey participants were above 50.

3.2 Presentation of Findings

This section presents the results from the data analysis. This study assessed the influence of resource needs assessment on academic performance of students with disabilities in integrated basic education schools in Nyarugenge district, Rwanda. The findings are presented and discussed as follows:

Table 2: Influence of resource needs assessment on academic performance of students with disabilities

Statement	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly Agree		Total N	Mean	Sd
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%			
I regularly participate in identifying the learning needs of students with disabilities.	0	0.0	67	25.0	0	0.0	157	58.6	44	16.4	268	3.66	1.027
My school conducts inclusive needs assessments to support all learners.	0	0.0	0	0.0	27	10.1	172	64.2	69	25.7	268	4.16	.579
I involve parents or guardians when identifying the needs of learners with disabilities.	0	0.0	42	15.7	0	0.0	115	42.9	111	41.4	268	4.10	1.017
I use formal tools or methods to assess the learning needs of students with disabilities.	0	0.0	24	9.0	0	0.0	189	70.5	55	20.5	268	4.03	.752
Overall Mean											3.987		

Source: Primary data, (2026)

Table 2 displays the results of the first objective of this investigation to assess the influence of resource needs assessment on academic performance of students with disabilities in integrated basic education schools in Nyarugenge district, Rwanda. Out of 268 respondents, the results were examined, 25.0% disagreed, 58.6% agreed and 16.4% strongly agreed that they regularly participate in identifying the learning needs of students with disabilities. On their school conducts inclusive needs assessments to support all learners, the 10.1% were neutral, 64.2% agreed, and 25.7% strongly agreed.

The 15.7% disagreed, 42.9% agreed, and 41.4% strongly agreed that they involve parents or guardians when identifying the needs of learners with disabilities. Out of 268 respondents surveyed, 9.0% disagreed, 70.5% agreed, and 20.5% strongly agreed that they use formal tools or methods to assess the learning needs of students with disabilities. The overall means of results was 3.987 that was between neutral (3) and agree (4), which indicated that there was significant influence of resource needs assessment on academic performance of students with disabilities in integrated basic education schools in Nyarugenge district, Rwanda.

Table 3: Model Summary of resource needs assessment and academic performance of students with disabilities

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.896 ^a	.804	.803	.414

a. Predictors: (Constant), Inclusive Resources Needs Assessment

Source: Primary data, (2026)

Table 3 displays the model summary of the assessment of students with disabilities' resource needs and academic performance. According to the findings, R Square = 0.804. It was evident that one of the variables of the resource needs assessment of integrated basic education schools in the Nyarugenge district, Rwanda might have an influence on 80.3% of all variables of the academic performance of students with disabilities.

3.3 Academic performance of students with disabilities

The dependent variables of the academic performance of students with disabilities in integrated basic education schools in Nyarugenge district, Rwanda were examined. The following is a presentation and discussion of the findings.

Table 4: Academic performance of Students with Disabilities

Statement	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly Agree		Total N	Mean	Sd
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%			
I have observed academic improvement in students with disabilities in my classroom.	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	132	49.3	136	50.7	268	4.51	.501
My students with disabilities attend school regularly.	0	0.0	90	33.6	0	0.0	145	54.1	33	12.3	268	3.45	1.082
I monitor and record the academic progress of students with disabilities.	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	164	61.2	104	38.8	268	4.39	.488
My students with disabilities are promoted at the same rate as their peers.	0	0.0	0	0.0	51	19.0	166	62.0	51	19.0	268	4.00	.618
The inclusive education support provided has contributed to better test results for students with disabilities.	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	153	57.1	115	42.9	268	4.43	.496
My school recognizes and encourages the academic achievements of students with disabilities.	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	125	46.6	143	53.4	268	4.53	.500
Overall Mean												4.22	

Source: Primary data, (2026)

Table 4 displays the results of the dependent variables of academic performance of students with disabilities in integrated basic education schools in Nyarugenge district, Rwanda. Out of the 268 respondents, the results were examined, 49.3% agreed and 50.7% strongly agreed that they have observed academic improvement in students with disabilities in my

classroom. The 33.6% disagreed, 54.1% agreed and 12.3% strongly agreed that their students with disabilities attend school regularly. On that they monitor and record the academic progress of students with disabilities, the 61.2% agreed and 38.8% strongly agreed. The 19.0% were neutral, 62.0% agreed and 19.0% strongly agreed that their students with disabilities were promoted at the same rate as their peers.

Out of 268 respondents surveyed, 57.1% agreed, 42.9% strongly agreed that the inclusive education support provided has contributed to better test results for students with disabilities. The 46.6% agreed and 53.4% strongly agreed that their school recognizes and encourages the academic achievements of students with disabilities. The overall means of results was 4.22 that was between agree (4) and strongly agree (5), indicating that there was significant academic performance of students with disabilities in integrated basic education schools in Nyarugenge district, Rwanda.

3.4 Correlation Between resources management and academic performance of students with disabilities

This study analyzed the correlation between the inclusive education resources management on academic performance of students with disabilities in integrated basic education schools in Nyarugenge district, Rwanda. The following is a presentation and discussion of the findings.

Table 5: Correlation between resources management and academic performance of students with Disabilities

Correlations		Inclusive Resources Needs Assessment	Assistive Technology Monitoring	Teachers' Training on Inclusive Education	Inclusive Education Resources Allocation	Academic Performance of Students with Disabilities
Inclusive Resources Needs Assessment	Pearson Correlation	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)					
Assistive Technology Monitoring	N	268				
	Pearson Correlation	.941**	1			
Teachers' Training on Inclusive Education	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000				
	N	268	268			
Inclusive Education Resources Allocation	Pearson Correlation	.922**	.951**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000			
Academic Performance of Students with Disabilities	N	268	268	268		
	Pearson Correlation	.932**	.953**	.945**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		
	N	268	268	268	268	
	Pearson Correlation	.896**	.917**	.937**	.958**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	268	268	268	268	268

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Primary data, (2026)

The results are presented in table 5. The aspects of of the resources management analyzed were; inclusive resources need assessment, assistive technology monitoring, teachers' training on inclusive education, and inclusive education resources allocation. Version 26.0 of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) program was used to compute Pearson coefficients. A negative correlation is indicated by a Pearson coefficient relationship between -1 and 0 while a positive association is indicated by a correlation between 0 and 1. Values between -1 and -0.5 indicate high negative correlation, values between -0.5 and 0 indicate low negative correlation, values between 0 and 0.5 indicate low positive correlation, and values between 0.5 and 1 indicate high positive correlation.

The results indicated that the correlation between (inclusive resources needs assessment, assistive technology monitoring, teachers' training on inclusive education, and inclusive education resources allocation) and academic performance of students with disabilities was .896**, .917**, .937**, .958** respectively. It was clear that there was the statistically significant correlation between the resources management and academic performance of students with disabilities in integrated basic education schools in Nyarugenge district, Rwanda.

Table 6: Model summary of resources management and academic performance of students with disabilities**Model Summary**

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.964 ^a	.929	.928	.251

a. Predictors: (Constant), Inclusive Education Resources Allocation, Inclusive Resources Needs Assessment, Teachers' Training on Inclusive Education, Assistive Technology Monitoring

Source: Primary data, (2026)

Table 6 displays the overall model overview of the management of inclusive education resources and the academic performance of students with disabilities. According to the findings, R Square=.929. It was clear that 92.9% of all students with disabilities' academic performance may be influenced by one of the elements of inclusive education resource management.

Table 7: Analysis of variance of resources management and academic performance of students with disabilities**ANOVA^a**

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
	Regression	216.079	4	54.020	855.451	.000 ^b
1	Residual	16.608	263	.063		
	Total	232.687	267			

a. Dependent Variable: Academic Performance of Students with Disabilities

b. Predictors: (Constant), Inclusive Education Resources Allocation, Inclusive Resources Needs Assessment, Teachers' Training on Inclusive Education, Assistive Technology Monitoring

Source: Primary data, (2026)

The analysis of variance of the resources management and academic performance of students with disabilities in integrated basic education schools in Nyarugenge district, Rwanda are presented in table 7. The variables were found to be statistically significant with a regression mean square of 54.020 and a residual mean square of .063. Furthermore, there was a significant correlation between the academic performance of students with disabilities in integrated basic education schools in Nyarugenge, Rwanda and the management of inclusive education resources, as demonstrated by F=855.451 and P-value =.000b.

Table 8: Coefficients^a of resources management and academic performance of students with disabilities**Coefficients^a**

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		
		B	Std. Error Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
			(Constant)	1.340	.057	23.630	.000	1.228
	Inclusive Resources Needs Assessment	-.021	.043	-.025	-.480	.632	-.105	.064
1	Assistive Technology Monitoring	-.119	.053	-.154	-2.252	.025	-.223	-.015
	Teachers' Training on Inclusive Education	.282	.044	.382	6.482	.000	.197	.368
	Inclusive Education Resources Allocation	.538	.043	.768	12.378	.000	.452	.624

a. Dependent Variable: Academic Performance of Students with Disabilities

Source: Primary data, (2026)

The constant coefficients of independent variables of the inclusive education resources management and academic performance of students with disabilities in integrated basic education schools in Nyarugenge district, Rwanda are presented in table 8.

The overall constant results with P-value = .000 indicated that there was overall significant correlation between the inclusive education resources management and academic performance of students with disabilities. In details, it was statistically no significant correlated between inclusive resources needs assessment and academic performance of students with disabilities with P value = .632, there was statistically significant correlation between assistive technology monitoring and academic performance of students with disabilities with P value = .025, there was statistically significant correlation between teachers' training on inclusive education and academic performance of students with disabilities, and it was statistically significant correlated between inclusive education resources allocation and academic performance of students with disabilities with P value = .000.

3.5 Findings from Interview Guide

The 9 head teachers, the 8 deputy head teachers in charge of studies, and the student focus groups were interviewed using the interview guide. Thematic analysis was used to examine the data. There was much discussion and analysis surrounding the data. The interview audio and the text were transformed into content.

Influence of resource needs assessment on academic performance of students with disabilities

To the head teachers, on inclusive resources needs assessment, to their schools identify the learning needs of students with disabilities, and who is involved in that process, they responded that at the start of every academic year and each time a new students are enrolled, as the head teachers of an integrated basic education schools in Nyarugenge District, they use a systematic and cooperative assessment procedure to determine the learning needs of students with disabilities.

The Special Educational Needs (SEN) coordinators do more thorough exams to detect particular academic and functional issues, while class teachers first undertake observations and ongoing assessments to discover learning impediments. In order to obtain background information on the students' conditions and prior supports, they schedule visits with parents or guardians and examine any accessible medical or psychological reports. To guarantee precise needs identification, they occasionally work in conjunction with district education officers and specialists.

The data gathered is addressed in staff meetings and utilized to create customized assistance plans, direct the distribution of resources for inclusive education, identify suitable assistive technology, and schedule pertinent teacher training. This collaborative method guarantees that the evaluation of resource requirements immediately influences treatments meant to raise the academic performance of students with disabilities at school.

To the findings from needs assessments influence planning and decision-making for inclusive education in your school, the results of needs assessments are crucial to their inclusive education planning and decision-making as the head teachers. They create tailored assistance plans and modify their school improvement plan in accordance with the specific academic, physical, or communication needs of students with disabilities.

The findings help them prioritize the purchase of suitable assistive technology, make classroom modifications to increase accessibility, and direct financial resources to the areas that need them the most. They provided guidance for scheduling focused teacher training in inclusive techniques, allocating teachers to specific classrooms, and setting up remedial programs. The results of the assessments are also used to track pupils' academic development over time and to include parents and district education officials in interventions. In this sense, needs assessments serve as useful manuals that inform inclusive education practices and, in turn, improve the academic achievement of our school's disabled children.

To the Deputy Head Teachers in charge of studies, on how they participate in identifying and addressing the academic needs of students with disabilities, they responded that the deputy in charge of studies, they take part by looking over classroom reports and assessment results to find students with impairments who might need more academic help. They create, carry out, and assess the efficacy of tailored learning plans in close collaboration with teachers and the SEN coordinators. In order to guarantee that students with disabilities receive the assistance they require to enhance their academic performance, they also assist in planning teacher training, allocating resources, and coordinating interventions.

In their view, how effective are the current strategies used in their school for assessing the resource needs of students with disabilities, they responded that because they include teacher observations, SEN coordinator evaluations, and feedback from parents and specialists, they believe that the present methods for determining the resource needs of kids with disabilities are quite effective in giving a thorough picture of each learner's needs. To guarantee that all identified needs are continuously met throughout time, there is still opportunity for improvement in terms of more regular follow-ups and methodical documentation.

To the assistive technology monitoring, on how they monitor the academic use of assistive technologies in classrooms, and what challenges have they encountered, they responded that to make sure that students are using gadgets to enhance their learning, they keep an eye on how assistive technology are being used in classrooms through progress evaluations, teacher reports, and routine observations. They meet with the SEN coordinator on a regular basis to assess the effects on academic performance, and teachers are expected to record how each tool is used in the classroom. Some teachers' lack of technological expertise, sporadic device issues, and making sure students utilize the devices consistently in class and at home are some of the difficulties we have faced.

They responded that in order to guarantee the appropriate operation and academic integration of assistive devices in their school, they first give the SEN coordinator and qualified instructors the duty of routinely inspecting and maintaining every piece of equipment. Teachers and students are given instructions and training on how to successfully integrate the devices into lessons and learning activities prior to their use in classrooms. In order to make sure the devices continuously assist academic growth, they also keep an eye on usage through observations in the classroom, instructor reports, and input from parents and kids. If necessary, they make repairs or modifications.

3.6 Academic Performance of Students with Disabilities

To the academic performance of students with disabilities, on how their school track and evaluate the academic performance of students with disabilities, they responded that in their capacity as head teachers, they monitor and assess the academic performance of students with disabilities using ongoing assessments, in-class tests, exams, and customized progress tracking that is in line with each learner's support plan. Teachers keep thorough records of their engagement, academic success, and skill development, which are periodically assessed in meetings with the school administration and SEN coordinators.

To make sure that interventions are quickly modified to improve learning outcomes, they evaluate progress over time and talk with parents about the findings. In what ways have they observed any changes in academic outcomes, they responded that the Head Teachers, they have seen observable gains in a number of academic outcomes for children with disabilities when inclusive education initiatives were put into place.

On how they track the academic performance of students with disabilities, and what trends have they observed, they responded that through ongoing evaluations, classroom assessments, exam results, and routine observation of customized learning plans, they monitor the academic progress of students with disabilities. During staff meetings and parent consultations, teachers and the SEN coordinators review the progress, involvement, and skill development that have been documented. Students who regularly get focused support and inclusive resources have shown positive trends over time, including higher test scores, greater classroom engagement, higher attendance, and better promotion rates.

To their experience, what is the relationship between inclusive resource support and students' academic performance, they responded that according to their observations, there is a significant positive correlation between inclusive resource support and students' academic performance since students with disabilities may participate completely in classes when they have access to modified materials and teacher help. Academic performance, on the other hand, frequently stagnates when resources are inadequate or poorly managed, underscoring the vital role that inclusive, efficient resource management plays in promoting student performance.

On how the support or resources students receive at school affected their performance in class or in exams, they responded that the assistance and materials they receive at school have improved their comprehension of the classes and made it easier for them to finish their homework. They can participate more in class activities and follow lessons without falling behind with the use of assistive technology, modified books, and more teacher assistance. Their overall performance and exam results have improved as a result of this, as comparison to before they received these aids. They responded that teachers provide children with extra help when they are struggling academically, such as one-on-one instruction, small group meetings, or extra practice tasks. Additionally, they simplify complex subjects and occasionally employ assistive technology or visual aids to improve their understanding.

4. DISCUSSION OF STUDY FINDINGS

This study assessed the influence of resource needs assessment on academic performance of students with disabilities in integrated basic education schools in Nyarugenge district, Rwanda. Researcher reviewed the related literature. Munyoro (2022) examined the effectiveness of needs assessment practices in identifying resource gaps for students with disabilities in public schools in Kenya. The study revealed that while schools attempted to identify learners' needs, there was limited use of systematic tools and stakeholder input in the process.

The study recommended the adoption of participatory assessment frameworks to ensure accurate identification of inclusive education resource requirements. These findings underscore the importance of structured and collaborative needs assessment mechanisms in ensuring resources are allocated where they are most needed.

The current study showed that out of 268 respondents, 75.0% agreed that head teachers regularly participate in identifying the learning needs of students with disabilities and 89.9% agreed that their school conducts inclusive needs assessments to support all students with disabilities. In Ghana, Osei and Boamah (2021) investigated how inclusive education resource needs are determined and addressed in basic schools. The study applied a mixed-methods design and found that many schools rely on assumptions or outdated reports rather than current assessments of student needs. This study indicated that 84.3% agreed that schools involve parents or guardians when identifying the needs of students with disabilities.

5. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION OF FINDINGS

The objective of the study was to assess the influence of resource needs assessment on academic performance of students with disabilities in integrated basic education schools in Nyarugenge district, Rwanda, out of 268 respondents, 58.6% agreed and 16.4% strongly agreed that they regularly participate in identifying the learning needs of students with disabilities and 64.2% agreed that their school conducts inclusive needs assessments to support all learners. The 70.5% agreed that they use formal tools or methods to assess the learning needs of students with disabilities.

The overall means of results was 3.987 that was between neutral (3) and agree (4), which indicated that there was significant influence of resource needs assessment on academic performance of students with disabilities in integrated basic education schools. According to the findings, R Square = 0.804. It was evident that one of the variables of the resource needs assessment of integrated basic education schools in the Nyarugenge district, Rwanda might have an influence on 80.3% of all variables of the academic performance of students with disabilities.

The study concluded that there was a significant influence of resource needs assessment on the academic performance of students with disabilities.

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